

Master in Sound and Music Computing
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Freesound Loop Generator

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Abstract

This project investigates the synthesis of new audio loops using neural networks, focusing on creative sound generation through latent space manipulation. Using the FreeSound Loop Dataset, audio samples were preprocessed through tempo normalization as well as beat and downbeat alignment to ensure rhythmic consistency and structural coherence, enabling musically relevant synthesis.

The system is built around a neural autoencoder, specifically the RAVE model, which compresses audio loops into compact latent representations and reconstructs them with high-fidelity. New loops are generated by interpolating between two encoded examples, producing smooth transitions and hybrid sounds that blend characteristics from both sources. Genre classification guides latent space traversal, supporting stylistic selection and controlled blending of sounds. Furthermore, real-time manipulation of individual latent dimensions expands the system's potential for interactive audio applications, such as live performances or dynamic sound design.

Subjective evaluation demonstrated that interpolated loops are perceptually coherent and musically meaningful. Listeners reported that latent space trajectories provide expressive and controllable tools for creative composition, and, that varying the number of latent dimensions influences musical richness without compromising perceptual continuity.

By combining deep generative models, musically informed preprocessing, and user-controllable synthesis techniques, this work presents a flexible framework for creative loop-based audio generation, bridging high-quality synthesis with practical usability.

Keywords: Audio Generation; Neural Audio Synthesis; Latent Space Interpolation; Interactive Sound Design; Loop-Based Music

Chapter 1

Introduction

Sound synthesis has been a central tool in music production, enabling artists to create, modify, and explore timbres beyond the limits of acoustic instruments. Early approaches [1] [2] such as subtractive and additive synthesis, frequency modulation (FM), and granular techniques provided musicians with powerful, though often technically demanding, methods for shaping sounds. Sampling expanded creative possibilities by allowing the reuse and manipulation of recorded materials, forming the basis of many contemporary production practices. While these techniques established the foundations for modern approaches such as sound design and audio manipulation, they remain constrained in their ability to generate truly novel sounds or to offer intuitive, high-level control over complex sonic transformations.

In recent years, advances in artificial intelligence have introduced a new paradigm for sound generation. Neural audio synthesis (NAS), based on generative models such as variational autoencoders (VAEs) [3], generative adversarial networks (GANs) [4], and more recently diffusion [5] [6] and transformer [7] architectures, has demonstrated the ability to produce audio with realism and stylistic diversity. Unlike traditional synthesis methods, these models learn directly from data, capturing high-level patterns in rhythm, timbre, and texture. This shift has redefined how computational tools can support musical creativity, offering approaches that go beyond imitation of instruments towards the creation of entirely new sonic possibil-

ities.

A particularly promising aspect of these models lies in their latent space representations—lower-dimensional abstractions of audio that capture its essential features, such as timbre, rhythm, or texture [8]. Within this space, sounds with similar characteristics are typically positioned closer together, enabling smooth interpolations that often align with perceptual similarity. For musicians, latent spaces provide a conceptual bridge between the technical precision of synthesis parameters and the intuitive experience of shaping sound in real-time. Such capabilities open new possibilities for creative production, especially in contexts that rely on loops, samples, and interactive manipulation.

1.1 Motivation

This project is motivated by the growing demand for innovative music production tools that empower artists and producers to create unique, high-quality audio content. Advances in neural audio synthesis (NAS) and generative models have already begun to influence the field of computer music. For example, OpenAI’s Jukebox [9] can generate music in different genres and styles; Google’s MusicLM [10] uses natural language to condition music generation; and Magenta’s DDSP [11] offers interpretable synthesis parameters by combining neural networks with signal processing techniques, though its scope is limited to specific instruments.

Despite these advances, many existing approaches remain constrained by high computational cost—Jukebox—, lack of real-time interaction—MusicML—, or limited controllability—Magenta’s DDSP. In particular, loop-based music production and live performance require tools not only to produce coherent and musically meaningful audio, but also allow intuitive, fine-grained manipulation of sound. Current methods often prioritize output quality at the expense of controllability, leaving a gap for approaches that enable both. By exploring latent space manipulation and real-time control techniques, this research seeks to contribute to the development of interactive audio systems that expand creative possibilities in both studio workflows and live performance

contexts.

On a personal note, as a musician invested in the use of plugins and digital tools for production, I have been particularly excited by the potential of generative models. These models enable the creation of sounds that are intermediate between two existing audios—a concept that is both conceptually challenging and creatively inspiring. The ability to transform, modulate, and generate entirely new intermediate sounds sparked my interest in this research. The remarkable possibilities offered by latent space manipulation allow for unprecedented control over sound creation, which is especially significant in the context of music production. Loops and samples, central tools for many artists, become even more powerful when augmented with generative techniques, providing new sources of inspiration and creative exploration.

1.2 Research Objectives

The primary objective of this thesis is to develop a generative audio system for creative sound loop manipulation. Specifically, this research aims to:

- Synthesize and interpolate audio loops from the FreeSound Dataset.
- Enable mashup loop synthesis and style mixing through latent space manipulation.
- Explore how navigating the model’s latent space can facilitate dynamic and intuitive modification of the generated audio output.

To achieve these objectives, the study addresses several research questions focused on the perceptual, musical, and usability aspects of latent space manipulation in generative models:

1. To what extent are interpolations between latent representations perceptually meaningful and musically coherent in terms of musical features (e.g., rhythm, timbre) ?

2. Can latent space interpolation in generative audio models like RAVE be leveraged to synthesize musically usable transitions —such as seamless genre blending or timbral morphing— within loop-based music?
3. How does varying the fidelity parameter in RAVE’s latent space dimensionality reduction affect the perceptual continuity and expressiveness (defined as the perceived richness and quality of audio detail) of interpolated audio transitions between diverse musical inputs?

Corresponding to the research questions above, the study tests the following hypotheses:

Perceptual blend and musical coherence (RQ1): It is hypothesized that interpolated audio at the midpoint between two latent representations will be perceived by listeners as a meaning blend of both source loops, and that the interpolated transitions will be rated as musically coherent, exhibiting perceptually logical changes in rhythm, timbre, and structure.

Usability and control mapping (RQ2): It is hypothesized that listeners will find interpolated transitions as musically usable in loop-based composition, and that they can reliably perceive and describe the direction of the morph as it progresses from one genre to another.

Latent space fidelity (RQ3): It is hypothesized that reducing the fidelity parameter in RAVE’s latent representation will negatively affect the expressiveness of interpolated audio transitions, while not significantly disrupting perceptual continuity.

1.3 Structure of the Thesis

The remainder of this thesis is organized as follows:

- **Chapter 2** reviews the state of the art , discussing generative models for audio and latent space manipulation, including variational autoencoders, trans-

former models, GANs, diffusion models, and hybrid approaches.

- **Chapter 3** details the methodology, covering dataset selection and preparation, exploratory analysis, model design for real-time latent representation, training, inference system implementation, evaluation metrics, and experimental procedures.
- **Chapter 4** presents the outcomes of the evaluation of the proposed system, reporting listener responses, intensity and agreement measures, identified musical dimensions, and comparisons of morphing strategies.
- **Chapter 5** discusses the implications of the findings, draws conclusions, and outlines directions for future research.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

The field of deep learning has witnessed rapid advancements, particularly in generative models. Traditional methods, such as variational autoencoders (VAEs) [3], have demonstrated significant capabilities in modeling complex data distributions through the learning of latent spaces. More recently, transformer-based architectures [7] have redefined how latent spaces can be explored and manipulated, offering good scalability and performance across various domains.

This chapter examines state-of-the-art methodologies relevant to latent space manipulation and interpolation, with a particular focus on morphing techniques across various generative models. Section 2.1 places special emphasis on variational autoencoders (VAEs) –particularly the RAVE model [12]– and transformer architectures, alongside generative adversarial networks (GANs) [4], diffusion models [6] [5], and hybrid approaches. The analysis of how these models synthesize audio provides insights into how architectural differences influence the quality and coherence of the generated output.

2.1 Generative Models for Latent Space Manipulation

Morphing techniques enable smooth transitions between different data points in the latent space, allowing for interpolation, attribute editing, and controlled transformations. Different classes of generative models offer unique approaches to morphing.

2.1.1 Variational Autoencoders

Variational autoencoders (VAEs) [3] are generative models designed to learn a probabilistic mapping from observed data to a structured latent space. Unlike deterministic autoencoders, VAEs introduce stochasticity through a probabilistic encoder-decoder framework, where the encoder maps input data to a distribution over latent variables rather than a single point. This stochastic nature promotes robustness and smoothness in the learned latent space, enabling meaningful interpolations and traversals.

The latent space of a VAE is typically modeled as a Gaussian distribution, where the encoder outputs parameters defining a mean and variance for each input. During training, latent variables are sampled from these distributions, and the decoder reconstructs the original input from the sampled points. The model is optimized by maximizing a variational lower bound, which includes both a reconstruction loss and a regularization term enforcing the latent space to approximate a predefined prior distribution, usually a standard Gaussian.

Early research demonstrated that VAEs could morph between distinct data points by linearly interpolating between their corresponding latent representations. Due to the continuous and structured nature of the latent space, transitions between points produce coherent, gradual transformations.

Additionally, the standard VAE framework often produces entangled latent spaces, where different generative factors are not well-separated. This lack of disentanglement makes morphing operations less interpretable and can cause undesired blending

of unrelated features during interpolation. Several approaches have been proposed to address these limitations by improving the structure and interpretability of the latent space. For example, hierarchical VAEs [13], they introduce a multi-level latent space architecture, where higher-level latent variables capture global structure while lower-level variables capture finer details. This hierarchical organization allows smoother and more coherent interpolations by modeling complex data distributions more effectively. Furthermore, structured latent space models, such as Beta-VAEs [14], modify the training objective to encourage disentanglement [15]. By introducing a hyperparameter β to control the trade-off between reconstruction fidelity and latent regularization, Beta-VAEs promote the separation of independent generative factors. Such disentangled representations enable more interpretable and controlled morphing operations.

While VAEs are well-suited for generating smooth transitions within a structured latent space, balancing reconstruction quality with meaningful latent representation remains a fundamental challenge. Enforcing smoothness through strong regularization can degrade reconstruction quality, leading to oversmoothed outputs that lack detail. Conversely, relaxing the regularization can enhance fidelity but at the expense of losing coherence in interpolations.

The RAVE model [12] overcomes several traditional limitations of VAEs by combining adversarial regularization and multi-resolution spectral reconstruction loss. This enables high-fidelity and real-time audio generation, making RAVE particularly well-suited for interactive applications such as live audio loop creation and manipulation.

2.1.2 Transformer Models

Transformer models [7] have revolutionized sequence modeling by employing self-attention mechanisms to process input data in a parallelized manner, bypassing the need for recurrent or convolutional structures. They learn contextual relationships over long distances, making them particularly effective for tasks that require preserving coherence across extended sequences. The self-attention mechanism com-

putes dependencies between all elements of an input sequence simultaneously, allowing transformers to capture complex patterns and long-range interactions that traditional architectures struggle to model. This capacity for understanding global dependencies is especially valuable for morphing tasks, where smooth transitions between diverse inputs are essential.

For example, LoopNet[16] employs attention mechanisms to capture temporal dependencies within musical loops. It learns to recognize patterns and structures over multiple time scales, facilitating the generation of coherent and continuous audio loops. Wave-U-Net [17], originally designed as a convolutional model for audio source separation, has been adapted with transformer architectures to enhance its capacity for modeling long-range dependencies. This integration provides improved control over generating structured audio outputs across extended sequences. Even MelNet [18], a model designed for generating high-fidelity audio spectrograms using hierarchical architectures, supports the generation of structured outputs that retain fine-grained details over extended durations.

Most recently, Transformer-XL [19], a model that is a variant of the standard transformer, addresses the challenge of generating long sequences by incorporating recurrence mechanisms. In typical transformers, the model’s attention mechanism is limited to a fixed-length context window, which restricts the ability to capture long-range dependencies. Transformer-XL solves this limitation by introducing a memory mechanism that allows the model to retain and reuse hidden states from previous segments of input data across different training steps. This enables the model to handle much longer sequences efficiently, making it well-suited for tasks like language modeling, where maintaining long-term dependencies is crucial for coherent output. This ability to persist memory over long distances is particularly useful when generating continuous data, such as long audio sequences, where consistency and context preservation are essential.

In addition, AudioLM [20] is a hierarchical model designed for high-quality audio generation. Unlike traditional models that directly generate audio waveforms or spectrograms, AudioLM leverages a two-level hierarchical approach to generate au-

dio. It learns to represent audio data at both low-level (fine-grained) and high-level (abstract). The low-level representations capture more granular features of audio, such as acoustic properties, while the high-level representations capture broader patterns like musical structures or speech context. The hierarchical nature of AudioLM enables it to model both local and global dependencies within the data. This makes it particularly powerful for tasks that require contextual accuracy, such as generating speech or music, where understanding both the micro-level (like phonemes or notes) and macro-level (like sentence or melody structure) is critical. By learning at multiple levels of abstraction, AudioLM can generate realistic audio that maintains coherence over long durations.

Transformers offer a powerful framework for modeling complex sequential data, particularly due to their ability to capture long-range temporal dependencies through self-attention mechanisms. This makes them well-suited for tasks requiring structural coherence, such as audio loop synthesis and morphing. Although most transformer-based systems in the literature focus on generation or translation tasks, there is growing interest in exploring their potential for latent space traversal and style conditioning. However, established architectures like VAEs currently dominate this space in terms of coherence and fidelity.

2.1.3 Alternatives Approaches: Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Diffusion and Hybrid Models

Generative Adversarial Networks

Generative adversarial networks (GANs)[4], have become a foundational tool for generating realistic samples by training a generator against a discriminator in a competitive framework. The generator aims to produce data indistinguishable from the real dataset, while the discriminator attempts to discern between real and generated samples. The learned latent space in GANs has been extensively studied for its capability to support linear and nonlinear morphing techniques. Such techniques include style transfer, attribute-based editing, and smooth transitions between dif-

ferent data samples.

For example, conditional GANs (cGANs) [21] introduce additional conditioning variables to guide the latent space exploration, giving users more control over the generated outputs. These conditioning variables can include attributes such as tempo, key, or genre, which can be specified to influence the generated audio or visual content.

Early GAN architectures often suffered from training instability and mode collapse. However, advancements such as StyleGAN [22] and StyleGAN2 [23] introduced significant improvements. These models proposed a style-based generator architecture where a mapping network transforms input vectors into intermediate latent codes. This approach enabled hierarchical disentanglement of features and fine-grained control over generated samples, enhancing the model’s ability to perform smooth and coherent morphing. Furthermore, StyleGAN3 [24] was introduced, improving upon its predecessors by addressing aliasing issues and ensuring better spatial consistency. This version introduced Fourier features and an improved generator architecture, allowing for smoother transitions and enhanced morphing quality by preserving geometric consistency across interpolations.

Recent work by Hung et al.[25] explored loop morphing using StyleGAN, StyleGAN2, and UNAGAN[26], showing that smooth transitions can be achieved across different domains, including visual and auditory data. Their approach demonstrated the effectiveness of GAN-based models in learning coherent, seamless transformations between different latent representations. In particular, StyleGAN’s mapping network allows for non-linear control over attributes, which has been effectively exploited in various morphing tasks. The ability to traverse the latent space in controlled directions enables transitions between attributes, styles, or even domains.

For audio-based generation and morphing, several GAN architectures have been employed successfully. UNAGAN demonstrated the feasibility of applying GANs to sequence-to-sequence generation, showcasing robust morphing capabilities in speech synthesis and music generation. Other notable models include Parallel WaveGAN[27]

and MelGAN [28], which have proven effective for high-quality audio waveform generation. GANsynth [29], in particular, introduced a GAN-based approach for audio synthesis that operates directly in the frequency domain, achieving high-quality, fast generation of musical audio.

Even with recent advances such as pSp (pixel2style2pixel) [30] and e4e (Encoder for Editing) [31], which enhance latent interpretability and enable more meaningful manipulations in StyleGAN-generated images, GANs remain less flexible than VAEs for structured latent interpolations. Their application to audio is still largely unexplored, making them less suitable for real-time, controllable loop morphing.

Diffusion models

Denosing diffusion probabilistic models (DDPMs) have recently gained popularity for their high-quality generative capabilities, offering a different approach to generative modeling compared to variational autoencoders (VAEs) and generative adversarial networks (GANs). Unlike these models, diffusion models use an iterative process to gradually transform noise into meaningful samples through a sequence of denoising steps.

The foundational work by Sohl-Dickstein et al. [6] introduced the idea of using a Markov chain to progressively add noise to data, effectively destroying its structure over several time steps. By learning to reverse this process, a model can generate realistic samples from pure noise. This formulation laid the groundwork for more advanced diffusion models by defining a structured generative process governed by probabilistic transitions. Further refinement came with the work of Ho et al. [5], which introduced a simpler and more efficient training objective known as the denoising score-matching loss. This approach improved training stability and generation quality by optimizing the model to predict the original data from a corrupted version at each time step, rather than directly modeling the entire reverse process.

Recent diffusion-based models, such as Imagen [32], which employs a cascaded diffusion process conditioned on text descriptions, and Stable Diffusion [33], which introduces a latent diffusion approach wherein the generative process operates in

a compressed latent space rather than directly in pixel space, have demonstrated highly efficient and scalable generation. These approaches not only achieve state-of-the-art photorealistic image synthesis but also support controlled interpolation and morphing through latent conditioning, text prompts, or attribute guidance.

The iterative nature of the denoising process allows for finer control over generated samples, making them particularly effective for morphing tasks. During interpolation, they can produce smooth and coherent transitions by operating at various noise levels. This approach prevents abrupt or unrealistic transformations, providing a structured mechanism for generating continuous morphs. Furthermore, the flexibility of diffusion models allows them to be guided by external inputs (e.g., text prompts or conditioning vectors), enabling controlled and interpretable interpolations.

However, diffusion models are computationally demanding, often requiring hundreds of iterative steps to generate a single sample. Although latent diffusion variants reduce this burden to some extent, real-time or interactive applications—such as loop morphing in performance contexts—remain impractical due to latency and resource requirements.

Hybrid Approaches

Combining different generative model architectures leverages the strengths of each to create models that are more capable of handling complex tasks, especially when these tasks require both high-fidelity generation and coherent temporal structure. Hybrid approaches typically involve combining two or more model types—such as GANs, RNNs, transformers, and diffusion models—to improve overall performance.

A hybrid approach is to combine GANs—such as StyleGAN or StyleGAN2—with RNNs or transformers to address different aspects of generative tasks. GANs are typically effective for modeling high-quality structures such as images or audio textures. RNNs and transformers, on the other hand, excel at capturing temporal dependencies and sequential structure, making them ideal for tasks like modeling musical rhythms, progressions, or coherence over time. For example, in Style-conditioned

Music Generation with Transformer-GANs by Wang et al. [34] the authors present a music generation algorithm that creates compositions from scratch based on specified target styles. It incorporates a style-conditioned linear transformer to model MIDI event sequences and a style-conditioned patch discriminator within a GAN framework to enhance the modeling of music sequences.

Some models like SpecDiff-GAN [35], FastDiff 2 [36] suggest using GANs to generate an initial structure or coarse representation of data, followed by diffusion models to refine and add intricate details. This method leverages the GAN's ability to capture the overall data distribution and the diffusion model's strength in modeling complex, high-frequency components, resulting in high-fidelity outputs.

These hybrid methods demonstrate that integrating complementary architectures can yield good results in generating complex audio loops, especially when aiming to balance stylistic diversity with coherent temporal evolution. However, models that combine elements of VAEs, GANs, and diffusion architectures remain complex to train, resource-intensive, and often harder to interpret. The added architectural overhead can also limit adaptability in interactive music-making scenarios, where efficiency and transparent control are crucial.

Chapter 3

Methods

This chapter outlines the methodology employed in this work. Section 3.1 begins with a discussion of the chosen dataset, followed by the preprocessing steps described in Subsection 3.1.1. Section 3.2 presents an exploratory data analysis, emphasizing the style distribution of the subset used to train the model. Subsequently, Section 3.3 describes the selected model for real-time audio synthesis and its training implementation, while Section 3.4 covers its inference process, associated applications, and modulation capabilities.

Finally, Section 3.5 outlines the evaluation metrics employed, and Section 3.6 concludes with an experimental study of a custom-built transformer model, including its dedicated preprocessing pipeline, model architecture, training procedure, inference process, evaluation metrics, and comparative results against the core system model.

3.1 Dataset

The FreeSound Loop Dataset [37] was selected for its rich combination of high-quality audio loops and detailed metadata annotations, making it well-suited for music analysis and generation tasks. The dataset comprises 9,455 loops collected from the Freesound platform [38], each annotated with tempo (BPM), musical key,

genre, and instrumentation.

In addition to these structured annotations, the dataset includes textual metadata, which was used to extract user-provided tempo and genre labels. To improve annotation quality and consistency, approximately 3,000 loops were manually labeled through a dedicated web interface.

3.1.1 Data Preprocessing

The audio preprocessing pipeline consisted of three main stages: time signature filtering, tempo adjustment, and beat detection with alignment. Raw audio files were processed through these steps to produce standardized representations with improved rhythmic consistency, ensuring their suitability for training the model.

Time Signature Detection and Filtering

To ensure rhythmic compatibility, the system estimated the time signature and retained only loops in 4/4 time. The estimation algorithm analyzed beat periodicity based on onset strengths.

To estimate the time signature of the audio, a method was employed that combined onset strength analysis with beat interval statistics. It aimed to infer the upper number of the time signature (e.g., 3 in $\frac{3}{4}$) by analyzing regularities in beat patterns.

Using `librosa`, the audio file was loaded and decoded into a time-domain waveform represented as a numerical array, with its sampling rate also retrieved. From this waveform, the onset strength envelope was calculated—a time series that measures the magnitude of spectral changes between frames—highlighting temporal positions where musical events, such as onsets or percussive hits, were likely happening.

Beat tracking was then performed on the onset envelope, producing a series of beat frame indices and an estimated tempo. For each detected beat, the corresponding onset strength value was extracted.

To identify potential downbeats `scipy`'s `find_peaks()` was used to detect peaks in

the beat strength values that exceed the mean.

The intervals between consecutive peaks were calculated and analyzed using a histogram to determine the most common spacing. This dominant interval was interpreted as the estimated number of beats per bar.

If the most frequent interval matched a common time signature –specifically 3, 4 or 6– it was returned as the estimated upper value. If the analysis did not yield a reliable estimate, a default of $\frac{4}{4}$ was used.

Tempo Normalization

To ensure rhythmic consistency across the dataset, a tempo normalization procedure targeting $\text{BPM}_{target} = 120$ was implemented. The process consisted of:

Tempo Conversion The speed ratio r was computed as:

$$r = \frac{\text{BPM}_{target}}{\text{BPM}_{original}} \quad (3.1)$$

Where $\text{BPM}_{original}$ is the tempo of the input audio and BPM_{target} is the desired normalized tempo. This ratio determines how much the audio must be sped up or slowed down.

Tempo Adjustment Methods Two FFmpeg-based methods were employed for tempo adjustment:

- **atempo filter:** This filter preserves pitch while changing tempo. It supports speed ratios between 0.5 and 2.0, meaning the minimum speed is half, and the maximum is twice the original audio speed. To apply speed ratios outside this range, multiple **atempo** filters must be chained together:

$$r = \prod_{i=1}^k r_i, \quad r_i \in [0.5, 2.0] \quad (3.2)$$

Where k is the number of filters needed to achieve the overall ratio r .

- *asetrate* filter: This filter changes both pitch and tempo by resampling the audio according to the speed ratio.

Method Selection The optimal method was selected by applying Essentia’s *RhythmExtractor2013* algorithm [39] to the outputs of the different tempo modification techniques, and evaluating their performance based on BPM accuracy. The method yielding the smallest absolute difference between the estimated and target BPM was chosen:

$$\text{method}^* = \arg \min_{\text{method}} |\text{BPM}_{\text{method}} - \text{BPM}_{\text{target}}| \quad (3.3)$$

Where $\text{BPM}_{\text{method}}$ is the BPM estimated from the output of a given tempo adjustment method, and $\text{BPM}_{\text{target}}$ is the desired BPM.

Beat Alignment with Normalization

To ensure consistent temporal structure across all audio samples, a beat alignment and normalization algorithm was implemented. This procedure standardized audio clips to a fixed number of beats while preserving musical coherence, and consisted of four primary stages: audio processing, beat detection, downbeat alignment, and temporal normalization.

Audio Preprocessing Each audio file was first loaded, and, if it contained multiple channels (i.e., stereo), it was converted to mono by averaging across the channels. This ensured that all downstream processing operated on a single-channel signal. The sampling rate was then checked. If the original sampling rate differed from the desired target rate, the waveform was resampled accordingly. This resampling was performed using a linear interpolation-based resampler, ensuring that all audio inputs were temporally aligned at a consistent resolution.

Beat Detection and Downbeat Estimation A two-stage method for rhythmic structure analysis was employed, consisting of beat detection followed by downbeat estimation.

Beats were first extracted from the audio using `Librosa`'s beat tracking function, which estimates the global tempo and returns a sequence of beat frame indices. If the number of detected beats was smaller than the expected for the time signature, downbeat estimation was skipped. Otherwise, the onset envelope strength was computed from the waveform. The detected beat positions were then validated by discarding those that exceeded the envelope's length, ensuring all indices referred to valid positions. Finally, the onset strength was sampled at each valid beat location to estimate beat salience, allowing the identification of beats with stronger musical accents that were more likely to correspond to downbeats.

Downbeat estimation combined onset strength and spectral harmonic content. Downbeats –typically the first beat in a bar– are generally both rhythmically and harmonically prominent. Onset strength was sampled at valid beat positions, and chroma features were computed using a short-time Fourier transform and synchronized to the detected beats. These features were combined to compute a downbeat confidence curve $C(\tau_i)$ for each detected beat position τ_i :

$$C(\tau_i) = \alpha \cdot \mathbf{0}(\tau_i) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{12} \mathbf{H}_k(\tau_i) \quad (3.4)$$

Where $\mathbf{0}(\tau_i)$ denotes the onset strength at beat τ_i , and $\mathbf{H}_k(\tau_i)$ represents the k -th chroma feature at beat position. The parameter $\alpha = 0.7$ controls the relative weighting of rhythmic versus harmonic cues. The number 12 corresponds to the 12 semitone classes in an octave, a standard representation in chroma-based features; summing across pitch classes captures overall harmonic activity at each beat.

Peaks in $C(\tau_i)$ were identified with a minimum spacing equal to the time signature, ensuring that the downbeats were appropriately spaced. The first strong peak near the beginning of the clip was selected as the starting downbeat, and subsequent downbeat positions were calculated by iteratively adding the number of beats per bar.

Confidence Assessment Beat detection was quantified using the coefficient of variation of inter-beat intervals, after which a confidence threshold was applied to determine whether to proceed with beat-based alignment or fall back to duration-based processing:

$$\text{Confidence} = \max\left(0, 1 - 2 \cdot \frac{\sigma_I}{\bar{I}}\right) \quad (3.5)$$

Where σ_I is the standard deviation of inter-beat intervals and \bar{I} is the mean inter-beat interval.

Temporal Alignment and Normalization The target BPM was used to ensure a consistent output duration across all samples:

$$T_{target} = \frac{N_{beats} \cdot 60}{\text{BPM}_{target}} \quad (3.6)$$

$$S_{target} = T_{target} \cdot f_{target} \quad (3.7)$$

Where T_{target} is the target duration, BPM_{target} is the desired BPM, N_{beats} are the number of beats to extract, S_{target} is the target length in samples, and f_{target} is the target sampling frequency.

For samples where beat and downbeat detection had enough confidence, alignment began from an optimal downbeat δ_{opt} that ensured enough subsequent beats to satisfy the duration requirement:

$$\delta_{opt} = \arg \max_{\delta_j} \{N - j : N - j \geq N_{beats}\} \quad (3.8)$$

Where N is the total number of detected beats and j is the index of a candidate downbeat. If no set of beats met the requirement, the first available downbeat was selected; if no downbeats were detected, alignment defaulted to the start of the audio.

The segment was then extracted starting from the chosen downbeat. The end of the segment was determined based on the target duration computed from the fixed BPM. If the available audio after the starting point was shorter than required, the

segment was looped to reach the target length. If it was longer, it was truncated.

Final Output

The final output consisted of a subset of 4386 audio files selected from those with an original tempo between 110 and 130 BPM. All files were filtered and processed to match a uniform tempo of 120 BPM. The clips were 16 seconds long, consisting of 32 beats in a 4/4 time signature and resampled at 44.1kHz.

3.2 Exploratory Dataset Analysis

The dataset used for training consisted of 5 hours of audio, corresponding to 1125 audio files drawn from the preprocessed corpus described in Subsection 3.1.1. To avoid ordering bias, the files were randomly shuffled prior to selection. This subset was chosen to provide a representative sample of the larger dataset while maintaining computational feasibility during model training.

To better understand the selected subset, an analysis was conducted focusing on the distribution of music styles and the classification of audio files according to these styles. This analysis made it possible to assess how balanced the subset was across different sub-genres and to identify potential biases that could have influenced model performance.

3.2.1 Style Encoding

The MAEST (Music Audio Efficient Spectrogram Transformer) model [40] was employed for automatic genre distribution and classification. It is a transformer-based model designed for music tagging. Unlike conventional CNN-based approaches, MAEST is optimized for short audio segments and supports multi-label classification over hundreds of genres.

In the pipeline, the audio signal was first converted into a log-mel spectrogram, using an FFT size of 1024, a hop length of 320, and 80 mel frequency bins. The resulting spectrogram was then resized to match the input dimensions required by the MAEST architecture.

The pre-trained checkpoint `discogs-maest-5s-pw-129e` was employed, which performs genre predictions on 5-second audio segments and outputs probabilities across 400 musical styles. To obtain meaningful activation probabilities, the auxiliary function `predict_labels()` was used; it applies a sigmoid activation and averages the predictions across time dimension.

The full 400-dimensional activation vector was used as the style representation to

analyze the distribution and classification of genres within the subset.

3.2.2 Style Activation Distribution Analysis

Median and IQR Analysis

To see how musical styles are represented in the dataset, the activation probabilities of the 400 style categories were analyzed across all audio files. Each audio file was associated with a 400-dimensional style probability tensor, representing the likelihood of each style being present. The **median activation probability** and the **interquartile range (IQR)** were computed for each style across the dataset. Figure 1 displays the top 20 styles ranked by median activation, with error bars indicating the IQR.

Figure 1: Median Activation of style probability vectors.

Electronic subgenres dominate top ranks, with *Electronic—Abstract*, *Electronic—Experimental* and *Electronic—Glitch* showing the highest median activations. This suggests a strong presence of electronic textures and characteristics in the dataset.

The IQR values further reveal the variability in style activation. Some styles, such as *Electronic—Glitch* show high median values but also large IQRs, indicating that they are often prominent but with substantial variation in strength across the dataset. In contrast, styles like *Rock—Goregrind* exhibit a low median combined a with wide IQRs, implying a more sporadic and inconsistent activation pattern. Meanwhile,

styles such as *Electronic-Industrial* present both low median and low IQR values, suggesting a small but consistent presence across the dataset.

PCA Projection

To further explore the structure of the style representations in the dataset, **Principal Component Analysis (PCA)** was applied to the 400-dimensional style activation vectors. Each style representation was projected into a 2D space defined by the first two principal components, which capture the most significant variance in the style probability distributions.

Figure 2 visualizes this projection, with points color-coded by their predicted parent genre. Parent genres were determined by averaging activation scores within genre-specific subsets of the 400 style categories and assigning each file the genre with the highest mean activation.

Figure 2: PCA projection of 400-dimensional style probabilities across audio files. The first principal components account for 36.14% and 19.76% of the total variance, respectively. Colors indicate predicted parent genre.

The PCA projection reveals overlapping cluster but also some degree of genre-specific separation. Notably:

- **Electronic** and **Non-Music** files are more widely spread, forming diffuse clusters, likely due to the diversity of styles within these categories.
- **Stage & Screen** and **Reggae** show tighter groupings, suggesting more consistent style activations across the files.
- **Rock** and **Hip Hop** appear more dispersed, though they exhibit localized tendencies, potentially reflecting hybrid or overlapping style characteristics.

This projection supports the idea that while many genres share stylistic similarities (as evidenced by cluster overlap), the model captures enough stylistic variation to organize files by genre in low-dimensional space.

3.2.3 Style Classification

Each audio sample was represented with a style probability vector, with each element corresponding to a sub-genre. These sub-genres were then grouped into broader parent genres, as listed in Table 1. Classification was performed by calculating the mean probability across sub-genres within each parent genre, ensuring fairness across genres with differing number of styles.

Parent Genre	Sub-Genre
Electronic	106
Rock	91
Latin	35
Folk, World, & Country	27
Hip Hop	26
Jazz	25
Pop	16
Funk / Soul	15
Classical	13
Non-Music	13
Blues	12
Reggae	11
Stage & Screen	4
Brass & Military	3
Children's Music	3

Table 1: Number of sub-genres (styles) associated with each parent genre.

Based on the classification procedure described above, Table 2 shows the distribution of the 1,125 classified files across parent genres. Genres not listed had no assigned samples and were removed.

Parent Genre	Number of files (%)
Electronic	195 (17.3%)
Rock	107 (9.5%)
Hip Hop	127 (11.3%)
Funk / Soul	2 (0.2%)
Non-Music	590 (52.4%)
Reggae	47(4.2%)
Stage & Screen	29 (2.6%)
Brass & Military	28 (2.5%)

Table 2: Number of files classified into each parent genre.

3.3 Realtime Audio Variational AutoEncoder (RAVE)

For the purpose of real-time audio manipulation through latent space control, the Realtime Audio Variational AutoEncoder (RAVE) [12] was selected for its high synthesis quality and low latency.

The subsections that follow provide a structured description of the RAVE model. First, the overall architecture and the two-stage training procedure are presented. Followed by a discussion of the latent space compression strategies for effective manipulation and the reconstruction approach from reduced latent representations. Finally, the specific training implementation used in this work is described.

3.3.1 Architecture and Training Strategy

The Realtime Audio Variational AutoEncoder (RAVE) is a deep generative model that consists of an encoder that maps input audio spectrograms into a compact latent vector, capturing perceptually relevant features, and a decoder that reconstructs audio from this latent representation. To achieve efficient real-time performance, RAVE employs a multi-band synthesis strategy, where the waveform is decomposed into several sub-bands that are predicted in parallel and then recombined. This architecture not only reduces computational complexity but also enables high-quality, low-latency audio generation. The latent space is designed to be structured and compressible, allowing for flexible audio manipulations such as interpolation between samples and real-time modulation of individual latent dimensions.

RAVE is trained with a **two-stage training procedure**:

- **Stage 1: Representation Learning**

In this phase, the model is trained as a variational autoencoder (VAE). Through it differs from standard VAE implementations by using the **multiscale spectral distance** [41]. This spectral distance is crucial for audio applications as it avoids penalizing irrelevant phase variations that would occur with raw waveform L2 loss. The goal is to learn a latent representation that captures the

perceptually relevant features of audio while being robust to phase differences.

- **Stage 2: Adversarial Fine-Tuning**

Once the encoder has learned a meaningful representation, it is *frozen* to preserve the latent space structure. The decoder continues training with a combination of three loss components:

- **Adversial loss:** To fool the discriminator and improve the synthesis realism.
- **Continued spectral distance loss:** To maintain reconstruction fidelity.
- **Feature matching loss** [28]: To match discriminator feature maps between real and generated audio.

This multi-objective approach ensures that synthesis quality improves without compromising the stability and meaningfulness of the latent representation.

3.3.2 Latent Space Compression Method

RAVE addresses the challenge of identifying the most informative dimensions in the learned latent space to enable more effective manipulation and analysis. The goal is to find the minimal subset of dimensions in the latent vector z that retains enough information for high-fidelity reconstruction.

The method uses **post-training Singular Value Decomposition (SVD)** to distinguish between informative and uninformative latent dimensions. However, applying SVD directly to samples $Z \in \mathbb{R}^{b \times d}$, here b is the number of audio samples in the batch and d is the latent dimensionality, would be problematic due to high variance in collapsed dimensions that have converged to prior.

To address this, a modified matrix $Z' \in \mathbb{R}^{b \times d}$ is constructed where each row represents the mode (most likely value) of the posterior distribution for sample i :

$$Z'_i = \arg \max_z q_\phi(z|x) \quad (3.9)$$

Where, $z \sim q_\phi(z|x)$ denotes a latent vector z sampled from the posterior distribution $q_\phi(z|x)$ of the encoder given an input audio x , parameterized by ϕ . For Gaussian posteriors, this corresponds to the mean distribution.

The matrix Z' is centered by subtracting the mean across samples, ensuring that collapsed dimensions (which have constant values) become zero after centering. SVD is applied to the centered matrix Z' :

$$Z' = U\Sigma V^T \quad (3.10)$$

Where $U \in \mathbb{R}^{b \times b}$ contains the left singular vectors representing directions in sample space, $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{b \times d}$ is a diagonal matrix of singular values, and $V \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ contains the right singular vectors, representing the directions in the latent space.

A fidelity parameter $f \in [0, 1]$ determines the minimal number of dimensions r_f to retain:

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{r_f} \Sigma_{ii}}{\sum_{i=1}^d \Sigma_{ii}} \geq f \quad (3.11)$$

Where Σ_{ii} refers to the i -th singular value in Σ , and indicates the contribution of each latent dimension to the reconstruction variance.

This allows any latent vector z to be projected to a compact representation $z_f \in \mathbb{R}^{r_f}$ containing only the most informative dimensions.

3.3.3 Reconstruction from Compressed Latents

For reconstruction, the compressed latent z_f is concatenated with random noise $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$ for the uninformative dimensions, forming a full latent vector $\tilde{z} = [z_f; \epsilon]V^T$, which is then passed through the decoder to generate audio. Here, ϵ is a multivariate normal distribution with zero mean and identity covariance, and $[z_f; \epsilon]$ indicates concatenation along the latent dimension.

The paper demonstrates that with $f = 0.99$, the latent dimensionality can be reduced from 128 to 24 dimensions for string music and 16 for speech while maintaining reconstruction quality.

3.3.4 Implementation of the Training Procedure

RAVE was trained for a total of 2 million steps following the two-stage procedure described in Subsection 3.3.1. The first 1 million steps corresponded to representation learning, while the second 1 million steps corresponded to adversarial fine-tuning. The `v2` architecture was employed, which is an improved continuous model optimized for faster and higher quality generation.

Several additional configurations were applied during training. The `causal` setting enforced the model to rely on exclusively on past waveform samples, which is essential in real-time scenarios as it reduces the perceived latency, although at the expense of reconstruction quality. The `noise` setting introduced a noise synthesizer in the decoder, which improves modeling of sounds containing significant noisy components. Single-channel audio input was also used to ensure consistent processing across the dataset.

After training, the model was exported as a TorchScript file for deployment. The `-streaming` option was enabled, which activates cached convolutions and ensures compatibility with real-time audio processing.

3.4 Real-Time Neural Audio Synthesis and Morphing System

The inference system was implemented using Max 8 by Cycling'47. In this setup, `nn~`, a Max/MSP and Pure Data external designed for real-time neural networks processing, is used to run the pre-trained RAVE model, enabling low-latency audio encoding and decoding entirely within the Max environment.

The system accepts live audio or preloaded files as input, enabling playback manipulation with parameters such as tempo and pitch independently controlled before encoding into a compact latent representation. This latent space serves as the basis for a wide range of audio manipulations, including interpolation between sources and real-time modulation of individual latent dimensions.

Through manual controls and signal-driven modulations (e.g., LFOs and ramps), the user can dynamically construct and alter the latent vector, producing expressive, real-time transformations of the synthesized output.

3.4.1 Playback Manipulation

Playback manipulation is applied to each of the two different classified genre audio signals before they are encoded into the latent space. This preprocessing step ensures that changes in tempo and pitch are captured in the encoded representations, allowing the model to generate output that directly reflects these variations.

Each audio is first recorded into a five-second buffer for further manipulation.

Tempo shifting

Tempo shifting is implemented using the `groove~` object, which plays back the contents of a buffer at variable speed. Tempo manipulation is enabled via the `@timestretch` attribute of `groove~`. When this attribute is set to 1, the object engages internal time-stretching, allowing the playback rate to be changed without affecting the pitch. This enables real-time stretching or compression of the audio

signal’s duration, which is useful for manipulating the timing of the audio while preserving its harmonic content.

Pitch shifting

Pitch shifting is handled independently from tempo shifting, ensuring that changes in pitch do not affect playback speed. The *groove~* object provides a built-in *@pitchshift* attribute that allows transposition of the audio playback pitch by floating-point factor, independent of tempo. Pitch shifting is dynamically controlled by a message sent to *groove~*, driven by a number box that enables real-time user input.

3.4.2 Encoding

The encoding process begins by loading two audio samples that had previously been manipulated, analyzed, and classified as different genres. Both audio files are processed using the `encode` method provided by *nn~* external. The RAVE model uses a latent space of 128 dimensions, of which only 8 were actively trained to carry informative content.

3.4.3 Latent Interpolation

For interpolation, the five most informative dimensions out of the eight trained dimensions were selected. The interpolated latent vector is defined as:

$$\mathbf{z}_\alpha^{(5)} = (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{z}_1^{(5)} + \alpha\mathbf{z}_2^{(5)} \quad (3.12)$$

Where $\mathbf{z}_1^{(5)}$ and $\mathbf{z}_2^{(5)}$ denote the subsets of latent vectors corresponding to the two encoded audio samples (e.g., Rock and Electronic). The interpolation parameter is given by $\alpha \in [0, 1]$.

The interpolated latent vector \mathbf{z}_α is then decoded to synthesize an intermediate audio signal, resulting in a smooth perceptual transformation between the two source audio samples.

During inference, an interactive slider is provided to control the value of α in real-

time. Two use cases are available: one applies a single global α across all dimensions, and the other assigns different α values to each dimension.

3.4.4 Real-time Synthesis

Manual Control over each Latent Dimension

The five morphed latent dimensions can be modified by a slider ranging from -3 to 3 – a typical range for latent variables. These sliders allow direct, manual adjustment for each latent dimension, enabling real-time control and manipulation of the generated output.

Dynamic Modulations

Sawtooth Modulation In the third dimension, a sawtooth modulation is added using the Max object *phasor~*. This modulation produces a periodic waveform that linearly increases from 0 to 1 over a period T , then sharply drops back to 0. The frequency of this signal can be adjusted in real-time, allowing dynamic control over the modulation speed.

This modulation impulses a periodic, linear ramp with sudden resets onto latent features, causing the decoder to interpret the input vector as continuously evolving along that dimension rhythmic pattern. As a result, the decoded audio exhibits cyclic changes linked to the feature encoded in the third dimension, such as: timbral shifts, rhythmic articulations or gating... Since this dimension encodes a real aspect of the input audio, the sawtooth modulation produces audible and musically meaningful transformations, with the waveform's frequency-adjusted via a frequency multiplier– directly controlling the effect.

Square Wave Modulation In the third dimension, a square wave modulation is implemented using the Max object *phasor~* followed by a comparison operator ≥ 0.5 . The *phasor~* generates a continuous ramp from 0 to 1, which is converted into a binary rectangular wave alternating between 0 and 1. When the phasor output is greater than or equal to 0.5, the signal outputs 1; otherwise, it outputs 0. This

modulation impulses a periodic, binary switching pattern to latent features, causing the decoder to interpret the input vector as alternating between two distinct states within that dimension. As a result, the decoded audio shows abrupt, rhythmic alternations related to the feature encoded in the third dimension, such as: timbral switching between two sonic states, rhythmic on/off gating effects, or binary dynamic modulations creating stuttering or chopping effects.

The modulation frequency and phase can be adjusted via a frequency multiplier and offset, controlling the number of switching cycles and their temporal alignment with the driving signal.

Ramp Modulation Similarly, the second latent dimension, is modulated with a ramp signal, controlled by the Max object *ramp~*. This modulation produces a linear, increasing signal that rises from 0 to 1 over a period of T :

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \frac{t \bmod T}{T} \quad (3.13)$$

Where t represents time and *mod* denotes the modulo operation. The signal resets to zero at the end of each period T .

The decoder interprets the latent vector as a smoothly evolving feature that resets periodically. This modulation produces continuous and predictable change in the decoded sound that reflects that attribute captured by the second latent dimension. It adds a gradual change in brightness and tonal glides.

Sine Wave Modulation To explore and extend the expressive capabilities of the model, a modulation in the sixth latent dimension is added, by applying a sine wave generated using the *cycle~* object in Max, which produces a continuous sinusoidal oscillation. The user can control the frequency and amplitude of this sine wave, enabling flexible modulation over time.

Since the decoder was trained with all eight dimensions, it expects input vectors with values in these dimensions, including the 6th. Although the encoder does not use or modify the 6th dimension during encoding, the decoder learned to interpret

this latent channel during training, associating it with certain audio features—subtler or secondary characteristics of the sound.

By injecting a controlled sine wave into the 6th dimension during inference, a low-frequency oscillator (LFO) modulation is created on that latent feature. This modulation results in periodic changes in the output audio’s timbre, dynamics, or other characteristics associated with dimension 6. The effect depends on what the decoder learned to represent with this latent dimension which includes subtle vibrato, brightness oscillations, amplitude tremolo or spectral shifts.

3.4.5 Decoding

Once the latent vectors are generated—either by direct encoding, interpolation, or manual modulated control, they are passed to the decoder section of the RAVE model using the `decode` method provided by `nn~` external. This decoding step synthesizes signals from the latent representations in real-time.

3.5 Evaluation Metrics

3.5.1 Subjective Evaluation

A subjective evaluation was conducted in which participants were asked to complete a questionnaire while watching a video. The video provided all necessary context to understand the project and was divided into sections to support the answering of specific questions. The goal of this evaluation was to collect targeted feedback to assess the effectiveness of the system and its alignment with the research questions and their hypotheses.

The complete questionnaire, including all nine questions and response options, is provided in Appendix A.

Questions 1, 2, 5 and 6 correspond to *Research Question 1*. These questions collectively evaluate whether interpolated audio is perceived as a balanced blend of both source loops and whether the transitions are musically coherent in terms of rhythm, timbre, structure... Specifically, Question 5 tests whether changes during the morph are perceived as targeting specific musical features, while Question 6 allows participants to identify which aspects (e.g., rhythm, timbre, structure) are most affected.

Questions 3, 4 and 7 correspond to *Research Question 2*. Question 3 evaluates whether the generated transitions are considered musically usable in a loop-based composition context, Question 4 tests whether participants can clearly perceive the direction and progression of the morph between loops, and Question 7 compares the perceived control of per-dimension blending against uniform blending.

Finally, Questions 8 and 9 correspond to *Research Question 3*, examining how changes in latent dimensionality (fidelity parameter) affect the perceptual continuity and musical expressiveness of the interpolations.

3.6 Experiments

3.6.1 Conditioned Morpher Transformer Model

In addition to utilizing the RAVE model, a custom transformer model was developed to perform audio morphing while incorporating conditioning on style and BPM (beats per minute) as the quantitative representation of musical tempo.

3.6.2 Data Preprocessing

The audio preprocessing pipeline consisted of four main stages: audio normalization, tempo adjustment, genre classification, and neural audio coding. Raw audio files from the FreeSound Loop Dataset were processed to create suitable standardized representations for the model.

Audio Normalization and Standardization

All input audio files were standardized to a consistent format with the following specifications:

- Sample rate: $f_s = 44.1$ kHz
- Duration: $T = 5$ seconds
- Channels: Mono (stereo files were converted by averaging channels)
- Target samples: $N = T \times f_s = 220,500$ samples

Tempo Normalization

To ensure rhythmic consistency across the dataset, an optional tempo normalization procedure targeting $\text{BPM}_{target} = 120$ was implemented, as described in Subsection 3.1.1. However, this normalization was not applied during model training.

Genre Classification and Style Encoding

The style embedding was extracted using the MAEST model [40], as described in Subsection 3.2.1 for classification purposes. Specifically, the pre-trained checkpoint `discogs-maest-5s-pw-129e` was used to obtain the full 400-dimensional activation vectors for the whole dataset.

Neural Audio Coding

To compress and represent audio in a discrete latent space, the Discrete Audio Codec (DAC) [42] was employed –a state-of-the-art neural audio codec designed for high-fidelity audio reconstruction. DAC encodes audio signals into compact sequences of discrete tokens through a fully convolutional encoder-decoder architecture, followed by Residual Vector Quantization for efficient discretization.

The 44 kHz DAC model with GPU-based encoding was used to ensure fast and uniform token generation across the dataset.

3.6.3 Model Architecture

The model employs a transformer-based encoder-decoder architecture with separate FiLM conditioning layers for style and BPM [43]. Within the encoder, audio tokens are processed through multiple codebook embeddings, with FiLM layers modulating features according to style and BPM. Representations from both source and target inputs are then linearly interpolated. Finally, the decoder generates output logits using cross-attention to the interpolated representations, incorporating the same dual conditioning mechanisms.

Figure 3: Overview of the model. Source(s) and target(t) inputs (x) are encoded (E) into latent space representations and decoded (D) into output (\hat{y}). Source (z_s) and target (z_t) latent representations are interpolated using $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ to produce z_{morph} . Conditioning vectors include $c_s = [b_s, \sigma_s]$, $c_t = [b_t, \sigma_t]$, and $c_{decoder} = [b_{decoder}, \sigma_{decoder}]$, with $c_{decoder} \in \{c_{custom}, c_t\}$. Where σ and b represent the style and BPM vectors, respectively.

A detailed diagram is provided in Figure 8 in Appendix B.

Input Stage

The model takes two audio sequences for morphing, corresponding to the source and target domains. Each domain consists of audio codes $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{Z}_+^{B \times K \times L}$ from $K = 9$ codebooks, a style vector $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}_+^{B \times 400}$, and a BPM scalar $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{B \times 1}$, where B is the batch size and L is the maximum sequence length.

Embedding Stage

Audio tokens from each codebook are processed through separate embedding layers (mapping from $V = 1024$, the vocabulary size, to $d_{model} = 64$ dimensions), then mean-pooled across codebooks and enhanced with positional encoding. The conditioning information (style and BPM) is processed through separate embedding networks:

- **Style conditioning:** Linear projection from 400 to 64 dimensions

- **BPM conditioning:** MLP with Linear \rightarrow LayerNorm \rightarrow ReLU \rightarrow Linear \rightarrow LayerNorm, which transforms the scalar BPM to a 64-dimensional embedding.

Feature-wise Linear Modulation (FiLM)

The model employs separate FiLM layers for style and BPM conditioning allowing independent modulation of features. Given input embedded features $x_{emb} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times L \times d_{model}}$, style condition $c_\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times d_{model}}$ and BPM condition $c_b \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times d_{model}}$, each FiLM layer computes:

$$\text{FiLM}(x_{emb}, c) = \gamma(c) \odot x_{emb} + \beta(c) \quad (3.14)$$

Where $\gamma(c)$ and $\beta(c)$ are learned MLP projections (Linear \rightarrow ReLU \rightarrow Linear) of the conditioning vector, and \odot denotes element-wise multiplication.

The combined FiLM operation applies both style and BPM modulations additively:

$$x_{out} = x_{emb} + (\text{FiLM}_\sigma(x_{emb}, c_\sigma) - x_{emb}) + (\text{FiLM}_b(x_{emb}, c_b) - x_{emb}) \quad (3.15)$$

Preserving both conditioning signals while maintaining the original feature structure.

Encoder Stage

Six FiLM-conditioned transformer blocks encode each sequence. Each block contains masked multi-head self-attention (8 heads, $d_k = 16$; masked to ignore padding positions), followed by Add & Norm, Dual FiLM modulation (as described in Subsection 3.6.3), a feed-forward network (Linear \rightarrow ReLU \rightarrow Linear), another Add & Norm, and a second dual FiLM layer. The output then passes through a latent projector (Linear \rightarrow LayerNorm \rightarrow ReLU \rightarrow Linear) producing latent representation of shape $[B, L, d_{model}]$.

Latent Interpolation

Source and target latent are interpolated in the latent space:

$$z_{\text{morph}} = (1 - \alpha) \cdot z_s + \alpha \cdot z_t \quad (3.16)$$

Where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ controls the morphing ratio, and z_s and z_t denote the source and target latents, respectively.

Decoder Stage

Six FiLM-conditioned transformer blocks decode the morphed latent using target conditioning. Each decoder block follows a structured pipeline:

1. Masked multi-head self-attention is applied first, followed by Add & Norm and the first **dual FiLM conditioning** layer, which modulates features using both style and BPM conditions.
2. The block performs multi-head cross-attention to the encoded memory, applies another Add & Norm operation, and introduces a **second dual FiLM conditioning** stage.
3. Finally, the features pass through a feed-forward network, apply a third Add & Norm step, and are processed by a **third dual FiLM conditioning**, ensuring comprehensive style and BPM modulation throughout the decoding.

The decoder input is zero-initialized with a shape $[B, L_t, d_{\text{model}}]$, where L_t is the target sequence length, and enhanced with positional encoding before passing through the FiLM-conditioned layers, which attend to the morphed latent representation. Nine separate heads, one per codebook, compute logits independently, each of shape $[B, L_t, V]$.

3.6.4 Training Procedure

Dataset Construction and Data Loading

A paired dataset was constructed from DAC-encoded audio loops. Each training sample consisted of a source-target pair (x_s, x_t) where x_s and x_t were different encoded audio loops, which enables the model to learn morphing transformations between different musical sequences.

The dataset loader was implemented with robust handling of variable-length sequences through dynamic padding and sequence length tracking. For each batch, sequences were padded to the maximum length within the batch, and attention masks were computed to ensure proper handling of padded positions during training.

Each sample contained:

- Source and target DAC codes: $\mathbf{x}_s, \mathbf{x}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times L}$
- Style probability vectors: $\sigma_s, \sigma_t \in \mathbb{R}^{400}$
- BPM values: $b_s, b_t \in \mathbb{R}$
- Actual sequence lengths: $l_s, l_t \in \mathbb{N}$

Curriculum Learning Strategy

To archive more stability during training, a curriculum learning strategy was implemented to progressively increase the complexity of morphing ratios over time:

$$\alpha_{\text{curriculum}}(e) = \begin{cases} \{0.0, 1.0\} & \text{if } \frac{e}{E} < 0.3 \\ \{0.0, 0.25, 0.75, 1.0\} & \text{if } 0.3 \leq \frac{e}{E} < 0.6 \\ \mathcal{U}(0, 1) & \text{if } \frac{e}{E} \geq 0.6 \end{cases} \quad (3.17)$$

where e denotes the current epoch, E the total number of epochs, and $\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$ is the uniform distribution over $[0, 1]$.

This curriculum begins with extreme values of α (i.e., pure source or target reconstruction), then introduces intermediate ratios, and finally explores the full interpolation space.

Loss Function Design

Training was conducted using a simplified morphing loss function that directly supervises the model to reconstruct the target sequence, regardless of the morphing ratio:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{morph}} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}_k, \mathbf{x}_{t,k}) \quad (3.18)$$

Where $K = 9$ denotes the number of codebooks, $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_k$ represents the predicted logits for the codebook k , and $\mathbf{x}_{t,k}$ are the target sequence tokens for codebook k . The cross-entropy loss \mathcal{L}_{CE} is computed with the masking to handle variable-length sequences:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}_k, \mathbf{x}_{t,k}) = -\frac{1}{|\mathcal{M}|} \sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{M}} \log p(\mathbf{x}_{t,k}^\tau | \hat{\mathbf{y}}_k^\tau) \quad (3.19)$$

where \mathcal{M} represents the set of valid (no-padded) time steps τ based on the target sequence length.

The model learns to decode the interpolated representation, as described in Subsection 3.6.3, into coherent audio sequences through consistent supervision against the target sequence. The morphing behavior emerges implicitly from the latent space interpolation and the FiLM-based conditioning mechanism.

Training Configuration

The model was trained on 2010 audio files using the AdamW optimizer and the following hyperparameters:

Parameter	Value
Learning rate	1×10^{-4}
Weight decay	1×10^{-5}
Batch size	4
Gradient accumulation steps	8
Effective batch size	32
Maximum epochs	300
Gradient clipping	0.5

Table 3: Training hyperparameters

The OneCycleLR scheduler was employed with a peak learning rate reached at 10% of total training steps. Gradient accumulation was applied to simulate longer batch sizes while maintaining memory efficiency.

Training Procedure

The model was trained using mini-batches of paired source-target examples, following curriculum learning strategy for interpolation ratios (see Subsection 3.6.4). For each batch, source and target sequences were independently encoded, interpolated in the latent space according to the sampled ratio α , and decoded under target conditioning. A morphing loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{morph}}$ (see Subsection 3.6.4) was then computed against target tokens, averaged across codebooks with full masking variable-length handling. Optimization used gradient accumulation over N_{accum} steps and clipping for stability. The full training loop is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Training Loop

```

1: for each batch  $(x_s, x_t)$  in training set do
2:   Sample interpolation factor  $\alpha \sim \text{curriculum}(e)$ 
3:   Encode source:  $\mathbf{z}_s \leftarrow \text{Encode}(x_s, \sigma_s, b_s)$ 
4:   Encode target:  $\mathbf{z}_t \leftarrow \text{Encode}(x_t, \sigma_t, b_t)$ 
5:   Interpolate representations:  $\mathbf{z}_{\text{morph}} \leftarrow (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{z}_s + \alpha\mathbf{z}_t$ 
6:   Use target conditioning directly:  $\mathbf{c}_{\text{decoder}} \leftarrow (\sigma_t, b_t)$ 
7:   Decode output:  $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \leftarrow \text{Decode}(\mathbf{z}_{\text{morph}}, \mathbf{c}_{\text{decoder}})$ 
8:   Compute loss:  $\mathcal{L} \leftarrow \mathcal{L}_{\text{morph}}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}, x_t)$ 
9:   Normalize loss:  $\mathcal{L} \leftarrow \mathcal{L}/N_{\text{accum}}$  and backpropagate
10:  if Step %  $N_{\text{accum}} = 0$  then
11:    Clip gradient by norm (max=0.5), update parameters, reset gradients
12:  end if
13: end for

```

Validation and Early Stopping

The model was evaluated across multiple fixed morphing ratios $\alpha \in \{0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0\}$ to assess reconstruction quality at endpoints $\alpha = 0.0$ and $\alpha = 1.0$, interpolation smoothness across intermediate values, and morphing effectiveness at the midpoint $\alpha = 0.5$.

Early stopping was triggered if validation loss did not improve for 15 consecutive epochs, preventing overfitting while ensuring convergence.

Model Checkpointing

During training, the best model based on validation loss was saved, along with periodic checkpoints every 10 epochs, a final model state at the end of training, and curriculum epoch metadata for resuming training.

This strategy supported training resumption and helped model selection based on morphing performance across different interpolation ratios.

3.6.5 Audio Morphing Inference System

The inference system implements a neural audio morphing framework that operates on Discrete Audio Codec (DAC) representations. It enables controlled interpolation between the audio loops using the developed Conditioned Morpher Transformer model, allowing control over musical style, BPM, and structural characteristics.

Input Processing Pipeline

The inference system applies the same preprocessing pipeline used for training data preparation to ensure consistency between training and inference phases.

Audio Preprocessing Given source and target audio files, the system applies preprocessing to ensure consistent format and temporal alignment, including resampling, truncating or padding.

DAC Encoding The preprocessed audio is encoded using the Discrete Audio Codec to obtain quantized representations suitable for the model.

Style and Tempo Feature Extraction The inference system applies the same style and tempo feature extraction methods described in Subsection 3.6.2. Musical style features are extracted using the MAEST model to generate 400-dimensional style activation tensors, while tempo information is obtained using Essentia’s RhythmExtractor2013 algorithm. These features are computed for both source and target audio files to provide the conditioning information required for the morphing process.

Neural Morphing Architecture

Conditioned Morpher Transformer model (CMT) At inference, the model takes source and target DAC codes, style and BPM tensors, and a morphing ratio. Optional custom style and BPM can also be provided, which are applied directly without interpolation. The CMT model generates logits for each codebook independently.

Multi-Codebook Prediction The model outputs logits

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_k = f_{\theta,k}(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times T \times V} \quad (3.20)$$

where $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ indexes the codebooks and V is the vocabulary size (1024), f_{θ} is the CMT with parameters θ .

Advanced Morphing Strategies

Gradient Morphing For smooth interpolation analysis, the system generates a sequence of morphs with linearly spaced ratios:

$$\{\alpha_i\}_{i=1}^N = \left\{ \frac{i-1}{N-1} \right\}_{i=1}^N \quad (3.21)$$

Where N is the total number of gradient steps, i indexes the interpolation step ($i = 1, \dots, N$), and α corresponds to the morphing ratio.

Custom Style Conditioning When custom genre is specified, the system constructs a style probability distribution by assigning a base probability value to the selected genre labels. The system supports both exact genre matches and parent genre categories that encompass multiple subgenres. For parent genres such as "Rock", the base probability is distributed across all matching subgenres (e.g, "Rock—AOR", "Rock—Acid Rock"). The resulting distribution remains unnormalized to maintain compatibility with the sigmoid function that the MAEST model applies to get the activations for all the labels. A base probability value of 0.3 is used, which corresponds to the typical model output magnitudes observed during training.

Custom BPM Conditioning The target BPM can optionally be specified for the generated sequence. The system converts the scalar BPM value into a conditioning tensor compatible with the model's layers, as described in the architecture (see Subsection 3.6.3).

Output Generation and Decoding

DAC Reconstruction The morphed codebook predictions from all 9 codebooks are converted to discrete codes using $\arg \max$:

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k = \arg \max(\hat{\mathbf{y}}_k) \in \mathbb{Z}^{B \times T}, \quad k \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad (3.22)$$

Where $K = 9$ is the number of codebooks, $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}_k$ denotes the discrete code sequence for the k -th codebook, B is the batch size, T is the sequence length, V is the vocabulary size (1024), and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_k$ are the logits generated by the CMT model for each codebook.

The discrete sequences from all codebooks are then combined to form the complete DAC representation required for audio reconstruction.

Audio Synthesis The final audio is reconstructed through DAC decoding, which converts the discrete token sequences back into continuous audio waveforms. This process reverses the initial encoding step, generating the final morphed audio output.

Metadata Preservation

The system preserves and updates relevant metadata throughout the morphing process:

- Sample rate information for consistent playback
- Chunk length specifications for proper DAC alignment
- Estimated audio duration based on sequence length
- Original audio characteristics for reference, including input dB and number of channels

The audio duration is calculated based on the sequence length multiplied by the standard DAC chunk length of 416 samples.

Implementation Details

The inference system operates on CPU by default but supports GPU acceleration when available. The pre-trained model specifications include:

- 9 codebooks with vocabulary size 1024 each
- 64-dimensional model embedding space
- 8-head multi-head attention mechanism
- 6 encoder layers and 6 decoder layers
- 512-dimensional feedforward networks
- 0.2 dropout rate for regulation
- Maximum sequence length of 3879 tokens

User Interface

A web-based interface was developed to allow users to interact with the inference system. Users can select source and target loops, adjust the morphing ratio, and optionally specify style and/or BPM conditioning. The interface sends these inputs to the inference pipeline, which generates the morphed audio in real-time.

3.6.6 Evaluation Metrics

Fréchet Audio Distance (FAD)

The quality of generated audio was evaluated using the Fréchet Audio Distance (FAD), a metric adapted for music and audio generation tasks. FAD quantifies the similarity between real and generated audio by measuring the distance between their respective embeddings distributions, which are obtained using a pre-trained audio embedding model.

Mathematically, the metric is defined as the Fréchet distance between two multivariate Gaussian distributions:

$$\mathbf{FAD} = \|\mu_b - \mu_e\|^2 + \text{Tr}(\Sigma_b + \Sigma_e - 2(\Sigma_b \Sigma_e)^{1/2}) \quad (3.23)$$

Where μ_b and Σ_b represent the mean and covariance matrix of embeddings from real audio samples, while μ_e and Σ_e correspond to the statics from generated audio samples. Lower FAD scores indicate higher similarity between the real and generated audio distributions, suggesting better generation quality.

The implementation provided by Microsoft [44] was used. Gui et al. addresses critical limitations of traditional FAD implementations by introducing sample size bias correction through FAD_∞ extrapolation, evaluating optimal audio embedding models (finding CLAP and L-CLAP to correlate best with perceptual quality), and providing curated datasets (FMA-Pop and MusCC) that better represent high-quality music compared to commonly used datasets like MusicCaps. Their evaluation across multiple generative models and subjective listening tests validates FAD as reliable perceptual metric when properly configured, making it well-suited for the music generation task.

In this experiment, this metric was used to compare the core morphing system based on the RAVE model with the Transformer model developed. To capture different aspects of quality, FAD was computed using three embedding models: CLAP-LAION-Music and CLAP-LAION-Audio, which have been shown to correlate well with both acoustic and perceptual quality, and MERT L4, which is more specialized for assessing musical structure and content.

3.6.7 Results

The proposed model was evaluated against the RAVE-based morphing system using the Fréchet Audio Distance (FAD) metric, based on the implementation by Microsoft [44]. The evaluation used 505 interpolated audio files generated by combining 11 source audio files, with interpolation steps ranging from 0.1 to 0.9 in increments of

0.1, along with their corresponding reconstructed versions. The reference dataset consisted of the 1,125 audio files used to train the RAVE model. All audio files in both datasets were preprocessed using FFmpeg to have a duration of 4 seconds, a sampling rate of 44,100 Hz, mono channel, and 16-bit depth.

The following results were obtained:

Embedding Model	RAVE model	CMT model
CLAP-LAION-Music	0.34	0.47
CLAP-LAION-Audio	0.35	0.53
MERT L4	5.88	8.59

Table 4: FAD Evaluation Results: Comparison between RAVE model and the CMT model

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter presents the results of the subjective evaluation, designed to assess the perceptual and musical qualities of the morphing system through a questionnaire (see Subsection 3.5.1). The questionnaire consisted of nine questions, and a total of 86 responses were collected.

Section 4.1, reports the analysis of seven questions evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale. Section 4.2 presents the results of the identification of musical features within each dimension, while Section 4.3 discusses whether per-dimension blending offers greater control compared to a unified morphing ratio.

4.1 5-point Likert Scales

Seven of these questions were organized into two categories: *Agreement Scale* (Q1–Q3) and *Intensity Scale* (Q4–Q5, Q8–Q9), with responses rated on 5-point Likert scales, where 1 corresponds to "*Most disagree/not at all*" (strong) and 5 corresponds to "*Strongly Agree/ Very Strongly*". Results are summarized as percentage distributions, with the median and mode reported for each question.

4.1.1 Agreement Scale Responses (Q1–Q3)

Responses to the Agreement Scale, which assessed perceptual balance, coherence, and usability of the morphs, are presented in Table 5.

Question	Main response distribution	Median	Mode
Q1	5.8% Neutral/Unsure, 59.3% Agree, 34.9% Strongly Agree	4.0	4
Q2	7.0% Neutral/Unsure, 47.7% Agree, 45.3% Strongly Agree	4.0	4
Q3	62.8% Agree, 37.2% Strongly Agree	4.0	4

Table 5: Agreement Scale Responses (Q1–Q3).

Participants expressed high levels of agreement across all three questions. The midpoint of the morph (50% blend) was generally perceived as a balanced combination of both original loops (Q1; 59.3% agreed, 34.9% strongly agreed, median = 4.0). Interpolated transitions were rated as musically coherent, with changes in rhythm, timbre, and structure perceived as making musical sense (Q2; 47.7% agreed, 45.3% strongly agreed, median = 4.0). Finally, the morphs were considered musically usable for applications such as seamless transitions, genre blending or timbre transformations (Q3; 62.8% agreed, 37.2% strongly agreed, median = 4.0).

The distribution of participant responses to the Agreement Scale questions is visualized in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Percentage distributions of Likert-scale responses to Agreement Scale questions (Q1–Q3)

4.1.2 Intensity Scale Responses (Q4–Q5, Q8–Q9)

The Intensity Scale, which measured how strongly participants perceived specific qualities or changes related to the morphing process, is presented in Table 6.

Question	Main response distribution	Median	Mode
Q4	64.0% Strongly, 36.0% Very strongly	4.0	4
Q5	68.6% Strongly, 31.4% Very strongly	4.0	4
Q8	52.3% Not at all, 47.7% Slightly	1.0	1
Q9	58.1% Strongly, 41.9% Very strongly	4.0	4

Table 6: Intensity Scale responses (Q4–Q5, Q8–Q9).

Participants consistently perceived the morphing as gradual (Q4; 64.0% strongly, 36.0% very strongly, median = 4.0). They also reported that the morph appeared to target specific musical features such as rhythm, timbre and texture (Q5; 68.6%

strongly, 31.4% very strongly, median = 4.0). In contrast, changes in the number of latent dimensions were judged to have little impact on the smoothness or continuity of the morph (Q8; 52.3% not at all, 47.7% slightly, median = 1.0). However, variations in latent dimensions were perceived to strongly affect the expressiveness of the morph (Q9; 58.1% strongly, 41.9% very strongly, median = 4.0).

The distribution of participant responses to the Intensity Scale questions is visualized in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Percentage distributions of Likert-scale responses to Intensity Scale questions (Q4–Q5, Q8–Q9)

4.2 Identification of Musical Aspects for each Dimension

Question 6 assessed which musical aspects –such as rhythm, timbre, and structure– participants perceived as most affected during the morphing transitions. The distribution of responses across the five dimensions is reported in Table 7.

Musical Feature	Dim 1	Dim 2	Dim 3	Dim 4	Dim 5
Rhythm	20.5 % (84)	40.7 % (81)	48.8 % (78)	0.8% (1)	–
Timbre	20.8 % (85)	12.6 % (25)	50.6 % (81)	57.9 % (77)	–
Pitch/ Harmony	20.5 % (84)	0.5 % (1)	–	39.8 % (53)	–
Structure/ Arrangement	19.6 % (80)	17.1 % (34)	–	–	–
Texture/ Layering	18.6 % (76)	29.1 % (58)	–	1.5 % (2)	–
No noticeable change	–	–	0.6 % (1)	–	100 % (85)

Table 7: Distribution of participant responses across different dimensions and musical features, showing both percentages and counts.

Overall, responses revealed distinct tendencies depending on the latent dimension. For Dimension 1, participants reported changes distributed fairly evenly across all features ($\approx 20\%$ each). Dimension 2 emphasized rhythm (40.7%) and texture/layering (29.1%). Dimension 3 was dominated by rhythm (48.8%) and timbre (50.6%). Dimension 4 showed strong emphasis on timbre (57.9%) and pitch/harmony (39.8%). Finally, dimension 5 was constantly perceived as having *no noticeable change* (100.0%).

The distribution of responses per dimension is visualized in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Participant-identified musical features most affected across dimensions (Q6).

4.3 Perceived Control: Uniform vs. Per-Dimension Blending

Question 7 evaluated whether participants perceived per-dimension blending as providing greater precision and control compared to uniform blending.

The distribution of responses is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Participant responses on perceived precision and control of per-dimension blending (Q7).

All participants unanimously acknowledge that using a per-dimension ratio felt more precise and controlled than using a uniform ratio.

Chapter 5

Discussion

The findings from the subjective evaluation provide insight into the perceptual and musical validity of latent space interpolation for loop-based audio synthesis.

With respect to perceptual blend and musical coherence **RQ1**, participants consistently rated the interpolated loop as perceptually meaningful and musically coherent. The midpoint morphs were perceived as balanced combinations of both source loops, and transitions were judged musically coherent, with changes in different musical aspects perceived as intentional and musically logical. Furthermore, analysis across latent dimensions revealed that specific dimensions corresponded to identifiable musical features, reinforcing the interpretability and musical validity of latent space morphing.

In terms of usability and control **RQ2**, listeners reported that the interpolations were musically usable within compositional or performance contexts. The gradual transformations were reliably perceived and appeared to convey stylistic characteristics associated with different genres. Per-dimension blending was consistently judged as more precise and controllable than uniform blending. These observations suggest that latent space trajectories can function as expressive tools for style fusion and creative manipulation.

Regarding latent space fidelity **RQ3**, varying the fidelity of the latent representa-

tions was found to affect expressiveness more than perceptual continuity. Although transitions remained smooth even at lower fidelities, higher fidelity settings were consistently associated with greater richness and musical detail, highlighting a trade-off between compactness and perceptual richness in generative loop synthesis.

Taken together, these results demonstrate that latent interpolation not only yields perceptually coherent blends but also affords practical usability in creative audio contexts. At the same time, they reveal that model fidelity can significantly shape the qualitative character of the outputs, being an important parameter for both design and evaluation of generative systems.

5.1 Conclusion

This thesis developed a generative audio system for creative loop manipulation, demonstrating how latent space interpolation can be used to synthesize, transform, and blend audio loops. The system enables perceptually coherent and musically meaningful transitions, supporting applications such as mashups, stylistic blending and audio morphing.

The evaluation confirmed that latent space interpolation offers perceptually coherent and musically meaningful transformations, showing its value as a tool for creative loop manipulation. Rather than focusing solely on synthesis quality, the system emphasizes controllability and expressiveness, aligning with the needs of musicians and producers in loop-based workflows.

An additional exploratory experiment with a Transformer model conditioned on style and tempo (CMT) further highlighted the challenges of balancing controllability with synthesis quality. While style conditioning showed potential, tempo conditioning was less effective, and objective evaluation revealed that its acoustic, perceptual, and ability to represent musical structure did not match the RAVE-based system.

Overall, this work confirms that neural generative models, when combined with latent space manipulation strategies, offer a practical and expressive approach for

creative loop synthesis and transformation.

5.2 Future Work

Future directions include the development of a plugin implementation system, which would make the tool accessible in common digital workstations (DAW) environments. This would allow musicians and producers to explore latent space interpolation directly within their workflows.

In parallel, improvements to the Conditioned Morpher Transformer model will be pursued. In particular, refining the conditioning mechanisms for tempo and investigating alternative strategies to enhance both controllability and competitive performance. A more comprehensive evaluation, including subjective listening studies, will also be necessary to assess the perceptual impact of conditioning and to better understand its implications for creative applications.

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Appendix A

Questionnaire for Subjective Evaluation

This appendix presents the full subjective evaluation questionnaire used in the study. Participants completed this questionnaire while watching a demonstration video of the system. The questionnaire is organized into three sections corresponding to the three demonstration parts shown in the video, with questions and response options provided for each.

A.1 Linear Interpolation in Latent Space Using a Uniform Ratio Across All Dimensions

Participants were presented with the first part of the demonstration video, *Live Audio Loop Synthesis with Neural Networks - FreeSound Dataset + Max/MSP*, in which two audio loops were encoded. A slider on the left enabled real-time interpolation between the loops, producing a smooth transformation from one sound to the other.

After watching this section and observing the transformations, participants were asked to answer Questions 1-4 below:

1. Does the midpoint of the morph (50% blend) sound like a perceptually balanced combination of both original loops?

Scale: Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral / Unsure Agree Strongly Agree

2. Do the interpolated transitions feel musically coherent — e.g., do changes in rhythm, timbre, and structure make musical sense and feel intentional?

Scale: Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral / Unsure Agree Strongly Agree

3. Does the interpolation between the two loops sound musically usable — for example, could it be used as a seamless transition, genre blend, or timbre transformation within a musical piece?

Scale: Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral / Unsure Agree Strongly Agree

4. Can you clearly perceive a gradual transformation in sound as the morph progresses from one loop (in a specific genre) to another?

Scale: Not at all Slightly Moderately Strongly Very Strongly

A.2 Per-Dimension Ratio Control in Latent Space

In the second part of the demonstration video, titled "*Per-Dimension Ratio Control in Latent Space*", participants observed how each dimension was individually morphed within the Max/MSP environment. These dimensions were identifiable as the five separate wires coming out of the encode objects after linear interpolation, leading into the decoder.

Participant were then asked to answer Questions 5-7 regarding the use of per-dimension ratio control:

5. Do the changes you hear during the morph seem to target specific musical features (e.g., rhythm, timbre, texture)?

Scale: Not at all Slightly Moderately Strongly Very Strongly

6. Can you identify which musical aspects (e.g., rhythm, timbre, structure) were most affected in the transition?

Multiple choice per each dimension:

- Rhythm — e.g., changes in beat, tempo, or groove
 - Timbre — e.g., the "color" or tone quality (bright, dark, buzzy, etc.)
 - Pitch / Harmony — e.g., melody shape, harmonic feel
 - Structure / Arrangement — e.g., buildup, breakdown, or change in loop form
 - Texture / Layering — e.g., thickness, number of layers or instruments
 - No noticeable change
7. Compared to uniform blending, did per-dimension blending feel more precise and controlled?

Scale: Less controlled About the same More controlled

A.3 Exploring Dimensionality in Latent Space

In the final part of the demonstration video, titled "*Exploring Dimensionality in Latent Space*", participants observed how changing the number of dimensions affects the decoded audio.

Participants were then asked to answer Questions 8 and 9 based on their observations:

8. When fewer or more latent dimensions are used (i.e., different fidelity settings), how strongly do you notice an effect on the smoothness or continuity of the audio morphing between sounds?

Scale: Not at all Slightly Moderately Strongly Very Strongly

9. When fewer or more latent dimensions are used, how strongly do you notice an effect on the musical expressiveness or richness of the morphing?

Scale: Not at all Slightly Moderately Strongly Very Strongly

Appendix B

Model Architecture

This appendix presents a detailed diagram of the model architecture. The transformer-based encoder-decoder structure, the FiLM-based conditioning mechanism for style and BPM, and the feature interpolation process—including the layers in each block—are illustrated. Figure 8 provides a schematic representation of the architecture, showing the flow of data from input to output and the application of dual conditioning.

Conditioned Morphor Transformer model (CMT)

Figure 8: Model architecture

Appendix C

Materials for Reproducibility

All code, demonstration videos, and materials necessary to reproduce the core RAVE-based morphing system are available in the project repository: <https://github.com/AdaSalvadorAvalos/freesound-loop-generator>.

This repository includes:

- All scripts used for the ML pipeline
- A pre-trained model checkpoint
- The interactive Max/MSP patches
- The demonstration video used in the subjective evaluation
- A notebook for analyzing the evaluation results

Additionally, a separate repository for the experimental approach is available at <https://github.com/AdaSalvadorAvalos/conditioned-morpher-transformer-model>, which contains:

- All scripts used for the ML pipeline
- A pre-trained model checkpoint

- Objective evaluation comparing the RAVE-based model with the developed model
- The web interface